

Multi-Model Deep Generative Restoration of Harappan Seals Using Advanced Architectures

Meriem Aoudia¹, Madeeha Balouch¹, Arwa Bayoumy¹, and Imran Zualkernan¹

Abstract

The restoration of ancient seals presents a significant challenge in archaeological conservation, particularly for artifacts from the Harappan civilization of the Indus Valley. This project investigates the application of deep generative models for image inpainting tasks on damaged Harappan seals. We experimented with different approaches to reconstruct missing portions of these seals, using a manually curated dataset of seal impressions as ground truth for evaluation. Our methodology involved training state-of-the-art inpainting architectures and assessing their performance through quantitative and qualitative comparisons against archaeological benchmarks. Among seven evaluated architectures, RFA-Net achieves the strongest performance (PSNR 26.53 dB, SSIM 0.888 on colorized data), demonstrating that multi-scale dilated convolutions best preserve the fine engraved detail of Harappan script. This work contributes a programmatic fracture mask generator and evaluation protocols for AI-assisted artifact restoration.

Keywords: Ancient Seal Restoration, Image Inpainting, Generative Adversarial Networks, Diffusion Models

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, American University of Sharjah, UAE

Correspondence

G00105691@aus.edu, G00105837@aus.edu, G00082596@aus.edu, izualkernan@aus.edu

1. Introduction

The Indus Valley or Harappan Civilization (circa 2600-1900 BCE) represents one of the most enigmatic archaeological corpora from the Bronze Age of South Asia (Witzel, 2019). One of its most enduring legacies is a corpus of thousands of small, square steatite stamp seals, each typically engraved with an animal motif, often referred to as a "unicorn," and a short sequence of Harappan symbols (Mukhopadhyay, 2023). These steatite artifacts, typically measuring 2-3 cm and found at almost all major Harappan sites, are viewed as markers of administrative, economic, or ritual activity (Mukhopadhyay, 2023). However, despite more than a century of scholarly effort, the Harappan script on the seals remains undeciphered. Only a few thousand inscribed artifacts have been recovered, and the inscriptions themselves are extremely short, averaging approximately five signs each (Mukhopadhyay, 2023). Moreover, many of these seals are broken or fragmented due to aging, adverse environmental conditions, or historical mishandling (Baglioni et al., 2021), leaving their iconography and inscriptions incomplete. This combination of sparse evidence, an undeciphered script, and incomplete preservation makes it especially difficult to interpret the symbolic and administrative functions of the Harappan seals.

To address these challenges, traditional restoration techniques have been proposed. However, such methods often introduce subjective interpretations that risk compromising historical authenticity (Mukhopadhyay, 2023). On the other hand, digital restoration methods, such as generative inpainting techniques, offer a promising non-invasive alternative (Sumathi and Uma Devi, 2024b). However, existing datasets for ancient seals are either sparse, low-resolution, or lack the specific damage annotations required for supervised inpainting tasks. This scarcity of high-quality, paired data is a significant bottleneck, as deep generative methods typically require large datasets for effective training (Palaniappan and Adhikari, 2017).

This research addresses these challenges by exploring the application of advanced generative deep learning models, specifically U-Net, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and diffusion models, to digitally inpaint missing fragments of Harappan seals. Recent studies have shown that these architectures can synthesize realistic and contextually consistent image regions, and have demonstrated their usefulness in cultural heritage applications (Zhu et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024). To train and evaluate these models, we introduce a curated dataset of 1,058 Harappan seal images, split into training, validation, and test sets using an approximate 75% / 10% / 15% ratio with a fixed random seed for reproducibility (Internet Archive, 2024). To the best of our knowledge, this research is among the first to apply state-of-the-art generative deep learning models to the restoration of Harappan seals. Our aim is not only to improve digital restoration accuracy and visual coherence, but also to contribute to the broader effort of preserving culturally significant artifacts through computational methods. This work connects deep generative modeling with archaeological research and offers a foundation for future studies in digital heritage and computational archaeology.

2. Literature Review

The application of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) to cultural heritage restoration has seen significant advancements in recent years, with particular relevance to the domain of ancient seal reconstruction. As demonstrated by (Nanetti, 2021), digital restoration methods must balance computational innovation with historical fidelity, a challenge acutely present in Harappan seal analysis due to the script's undeciphered nature. This section synthesizes three critical dimensions: archaeological context of Harappan seals, computational approaches to seal analysis, and the evolution of image inpainting techniques.

2.1. Archaeological Context

Harappan seals present unique conservation challenges distinct from other cultural artifacts. As (Witzel, 2019) establishes, these steatite artifacts contain complex iconographic elements including animal motifs, human figures, and the undeciphered Indus script. The physical characteristics, small size (typically 2-3cm), intricate carvings, and frequent surface degradation, demand micron-level precision in digital restoration. Traditional conservation methods documented by

(Baglioni et al., 2021) risk irreversible damage to these fragile artifacts during physical cleaning or reconstruction attempts.

Recent work by (Yadav et al., 2024) has demonstrated how 3D scanning and computational analysis can reveal previously indiscernible script characters on damaged seals. However, as noted in (Perrin et al., 2023), the absence of bilingual inscriptions (like the Rosetta Stone for Egyptian hieroglyphs) complicates semantic reconstruction efforts. This limitation makes Harappan seals particularly suitable for non-semantic, appearance-based restoration approaches using generative models. Crucially, our approach targets visual completeness of the artifact rather than symbol decipherment, avoiding the interpretive risks that semantic reconstruction of an undeciphered script would introduce.

2.2. Computational Approaches

Prior computational efforts for seal analysis have progressed through three technological generations. Early work by (Idris et al., 2016) employed traditional computer vision techniques like thresholding and contour detection for basic character extraction. Similar techniques including exemplar-based (Xu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022) or structure-guided (Cao et al., 2011) while computationally efficient, proved inadequate for severely damaged seals as they lacked contextual understanding of the script's structural patterns.

The introduction of deep learning brought significant improvements. (Kumar and Gupta, 2023) demonstrated how convolutional neural networks (CNNs) could outperform traditional methods in ancient manuscript inpainting specifically in character recognition, achieving 78% accuracy on partially damaged specimens, highlighting their ability to capture finer details. However, as (Kaur et al., 2020) identified, CNN-based approaches often produce blurry reconstructions which could introduce inaccuracies when handling the seal's intricate iconographic elements.

Current state-of-the-art approaches leverage generative models. The work of (Zhu et al., 2024) on Chinese character reconstruction provides a relevant framework, demonstrating how adversarial training can preserve stroke-level details in ancient scripts. Similarly, (Xu et al., 2024) showed that diffusion models outperform GANs in maintaining structural consistency for degraded cultural artifacts, a finding particularly relevant to Harappan seals where script continuity is crucial for potential future decipherment attempts.

2.3. Image Inpainting Techniques

CNN-based models form the backbone of many heritage restoration frameworks due to their ability to perform well in local feature extraction and structural reconstruction. Architectures such as U-Net have been widely used to reconstruct degraded visual content in historical artifacts. For instance, both (Kaur et al., 2020) and (Farajzadeh and Hashemzadeh, 2021) used partial convolution enhanced U-Nets to restore degraded manuscripts and pottery, showing the effectiveness of these models on small, irregular damages. However, these models often struggle with larger gaps, produce blurry outputs, and face generalizability issues due to limited dataset size.

GAN-based approaches, particularly those incorporating attention mechanisms like (Kumar et al., 2024), have shown exceptional performance in preserving fine details critical for Harappan script reconstruction. The dual-encoder architecture proposed by (Sun et al., 2024) demonstrates how structural guidance can prevent common GAN artifacts while maintaining sharp edge definition in reconstructed seal characters. Moreover, GAN-based models including standard and conditional architectures, such as DCGANs and CycleGANs, have also been applied to mural and manuscript restoration, showing improvements in texture sharpness and visual coherence (Jboor et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2023). While these models achieved strong perceptual quality, they often struggled with complex textures or relied on specialized loss functions for stability.

Diffusion models offer complementary advantages. As evidenced by (Huang and Hong, 2023), the iterative denoising process provides superior performance in handling severe, irregular, and large damage patterns common in archaeological finds. However, the computational overhead noted by (Zhong et al., 2025) remains a practical constraint for large-scale seal analysis.

Hybrid approaches present a promising middle ground. The GAN-diffusion framework of (Sumathi and Uma Devi, 2024b) combines the visual fidelity of GANs with the stability of diffusion models, achieving 29.8 PSNR on mural restoration tasks. This architecture’s two-stage process, first reconstructing structural contours then filling textural details, aligns well with the dual challenges of Harappan seal restoration: precise script character completion and iconographic element reconstruction.

The literature reveals that structure-guided GANs and diffusion models with attention offer the most promising architectures for Harappan seal restoration due to their ability to handle large gaps, stylistic variance, and symbol detail.

Dual-decoding Harappan seal glyphs and textures independently may be best accomplished with hybrid models that segment structure and texture (Lv et al., 2022; Sumathi and Uma Devi, 2024a; Sun et al., 2024; Deng and Yu, 2023), guaranteeing historical accuracy without compromising visual authenticity. Traditional physical restoration, fills, casts, or manual retouching, lacks quantitative metrics and risks irreversible material alteration (Baglioni et al., 2021); digital inpainting offers a non-destructive, versionable alternative clearly separable from the original artifact record.

Incorporating domain priors—such as edge masks derived from intact seal regions or crack-pattern templates from physical conservation records—has been shown to substantially improve boundary coherence in reconstructed regions (Baglioni et al., 2021).

The current literature reveals three key gaps that this project addresses: (1) absence of standardized datasets for Harappan seal restoration, (2) limited application of modern generative architectures to undeciphered scripts (3) Adaptability of recent deep models to restoration of ancient seals/tablets.

3. Methodology

This section outlines the comprehensive methodology adopted for the restoration of Harappan seals, encompassing dataset creation, pre-processing techniques, the architectures of the generative models employed, and their respective training procedures.

3.1. Dataset Collection and Preprocessing

A carefully curated dataset of Harappan seals was created as part of this study, extending the application of AI-based image inpainting to these historically significant artifacts. The images were manually collected from online archival document websites (Internet Archive, 2024), drawing from both Pakistan-based (Mahadevan, 1991) and India-based (Mahadevan, 1998) collections of Harappan seals. The dataset was split into 75%, 10%, and 15% splits using a fixed random seed to ensure reproducibility. All three splits are drawn from the same collection of intact seal images, with damage masks applied programmatically at training and evaluation time.

Furthermore, to investigate the impact of color information on the restoration process, two distinct datasets were prepared: grayscale and artificially colorized versions. The colorization was performed using a deterministic transformation that maps grayscale intensity values to a warm stone-like RGB distribution, designed to approximate the appearance of archaeological materials rather than relying on a learned colorization model.

The training images were subjected to data augmentation techniques to increase dataset variability and model generalization, applied via torchvision transforms: Images were augmented using random horizontal flips ($p=0.3$) and color jitter with brightness and contrast adjustments (factor 0.1). The augmentation process yielded a final training set of 795 samples for both grayscale and RGB modes.

3.2. Image Pre-processing and Mask Generation

Prior to model training, all seal images were resized to a consistent dimension of 256x256 pixels. A critical aspect of training inpainting models is the generation of masks that define the regions to be reconstructed. For all splits, realistic damage masks were programmatically generated using a polynomial fracture mask generator designed to simulate natural breakage patterns

Figure 1 – Overview of the Harappan seal inpainting pipeline. The process starts with pre-processing intact seal images and generating synthetic damage via a polynomial fracture mask generator. The resulting masked inputs are processed by seven distinct inpainting architectures, before the restored seal predictions are evaluated using PSNR, SSIM, and LPIPS metrics.

Figure 2 – Programmatically generated polynomial fracture masks simulating real seal breakage patterns. Damage areas range from 15-50% of total image area, covering corner fractures, edge fractures, and multi-damage combinations.

observed in ancient artifacts (Figure 2). The generator produces three types of damage: corner fractures anchored to one of the four image corners, edge fractures along a single side, and multi-damage patterns combining several of the above. For each damage region, a set of control points is fitted with a polynomial curve (degree 3 or 4), and jagged noise is added to the boundary to enhance realism. Morphological dilation and erosion with elliptical or cross-shaped kernels (3×3 or 5×5) are applied, followed by Gaussian smoothing. Masks are rejected and regenerated if the damaged area falls outside 15-50% of the total image area, ensuring a consistent and representative damage distribution across all training and evaluation samples. It is important to note that all damage patterns used in this study are synthetically generated from intact seal images, as no paired dataset of damaged and fully restored Harappan seals exists.

3.3. Model Architectures and Training

For this study, we implemented and evaluated different deep learning approaches for Harappan seal inpainting. This multi-method framework enables a comprehensive comparison of different generative paradigms for archaeological restoration.

3.3.1. Convolutional Baseline Models. Baseline U-Net (Ronneberger et al., 2015): The base U-Net follows a fully convolutional encoder-decoder structure processing single-channel (grayscale) or 3-channel (RGB) inputs through four downsampling blocks. Each block contains two sequential 3×3 convolutional layers with Batch Normalization and ReLU, followed by 2×2 max pooling that halves spatial dimensions while doubling channel depth ($64 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 512$ channels). The bottleneck expands to 1024 channels before symmetric upsampling through transposed convolutions. Skip connections concatenate corresponding encoder feature maps to each decoder stage. The final 1×1 convolution with Tanh activation produces the output.

Deep Residual U-Net (DeepRes U-Net): This variant augments the Baseline U-Net by replacing each convolutional block with a residual block (He et al., 2016) incorporating Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) channel attention (Hu et al., 2018). Each SE block applies global average pooling followed by a two-layer MLP (reduction factor 16) and sigmoid gating to recalibrate channel responses. The bottleneck contains two stacked residual blocks at 1024 channels, increasing representational capacity for capturing fine engraved detail in Harappan seals.

Context Encoder (Pathak et al., 2016): An encoder-decoder network without skip connections, following a DCGAN-style architecture. The encoder applies five strided 4×4 convolutions with Batch Normalization and LeakyReLU (slope 0.2), progressively compressing the input to a 512-channel bottleneck. The decoder mirrors this with five transposed convolutions and ReLU activations, ending with a Tanh output. The absence of skip connections forces the model to learn a compact global representation, making it a useful baseline for evaluating the contribution of spatial shortcuts.

Partial Convolution U-Net (PConv U-Net): This model replaces standard convolutions with partial convolutions (Liu et al., 2018), which normalize feature responses by the ratio of valid (unmasked) pixels within each receptive field. This makes the model explicitly mask-aware: features from damaged regions do not contaminate the reconstruction of intact areas. The architecture uses four encoder stages with partial convolution blocks (kernel sizes 7, 5, 3, 3) and a symmetric decoder with bilinear upsampling. A reduced learning rate of 5×10^{-5} is used for numerical stability. With only 4.05M parameters it is the most lightweight model evaluated.

3.3.2. GAN-based Model. Pix2Pix: The U-Net generator (Isola et al., 2017) employs a 7-block encoder (4×4 conv, stride 2, Batch Normalization, LeakyReLU 0.2) with skip connections to a mirrored decoder (transposed conv, ReLU, Dropout 0.5 on deeper layers). The final Tanh layer generates the inpainted image. A PatchGAN discriminator evaluates $2c$ -channel input pairs (masked image + real/fake output) through four 4×4 convolutional layers with Instance Normalization and LeakyReLU, producing patch-wise realism scores.

RFA-Net: The RFA-Net generator is built around a Residual Feature Aggregation (RFA) module (Liu et al., 2020). The encoder applies three convolutional blocks interleaved with max pooling, progressing from 64 to 256 channels. Each block is followed by an RFA module consisting of three parallel dilated convolutions (rates 1, 2, 4) whose outputs are fused by a 1×1 convolution and recalibrated by an SE block, with a residual connection. A 512-channel bottleneck with two stacked RFA modules is followed by a symmetric decoder using transposed convolutions and additional RFA refinement at each scale. The final 3×3 convolution with Tanh produces the output.

3.3.3. Diffusion-based Model. Guided DDPM: The diffusion model uses a U-Net backbone conditioned on the diffusion timestep via sinusoidal positional embeddings (Ho et al., 2020). The time embedding is passed through a two-layer MLP (SiLU activation) and injected into each encoder and decoder block via additive feature modulation. The encoder has three stages with time-conditioned residual blocks, and the decoder mirrors this with transposed convolutions and skip

Model	Dataset	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	Params (M)	Inf. Time (s)
RFA-Net	B&W	23.56	0.8760	0.0993	25.29	0.003
DeepRes U-Net	B&W	23.51	0.8737	0.1036	65.98	0.046
Baseline U-Net	B&W	23.09	0.8689	0.1129	31.04	0.017
Context Encoder	B&W	22.70	0.8598	0.1150	13.90	0.001
Pix2Pix	B&W	22.57	0.8475	0.1305	41.83	0.001
Guided DDPM	B&W	21.84	0.8569	0.1146	8.54	0.266
PConv U-Net	B&W	21.03	0.8451	0.1315	4.05	0.002
RFA-Net	Colored	26.53	0.8877	0.0979	25.29	0.002
DeepRes U-Net	Colored	26.34	0.8858	0.1049	65.98	0.001
Baseline U-Net	Colored	25.93	0.8801	0.1121	31.04	0.001
Context Encoder	Colored	25.63	0.8737	0.1136	13.91	0.000
Guided DDPM	Colored	24.77	0.8726	0.1144	8.54	0.267
Pix2Pix	Colored	24.37	0.8511	0.0789	41.83	0.001
PConv U-Net	Colored	23.94	0.8613	0.1274	4.05	0.001

Table 1 - Comparative performance metrics across all models and datasets (higher PSNR/SSIM is better; lower LPIPS is better).

connections. The forward process uses a linear noise schedule ($\beta \in [10^{-4}, 0.02]$, $T = 1000$). During inference, 50 denoising steps are used with mask-guided resampling (Lugmayr et al., 2022): at each step, the intact regions are replaced with the ground-truth noised value $x_0 \cdot (1 - m) + x_t \cdot m$, constraining generation to the damaged areas only.

3.3.4. Training Protocol. All models are optimized with AdamW ($\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, weight decay 10^{-4}) with a cosine annealing learning rate schedule (base lr 2×10^{-4} , min lr 10^{-6} , $T_{max} = 200$ epochs). PConv U-Net uses a reduced base lr of 5×10^{-5} . All models use batch size 8 and train for up to 200 epochs. The best checkpoint is saved based on validation PSNR.

All non-diffusion models minimize a combined reconstruction loss:

$$(1) \quad \mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{L1}^{valid} + 6 \mathcal{L}_{L1}^{hole} + 0.1 \mathcal{L}_{perceptual}$$

where \mathcal{L}_{L1}^{valid} and \mathcal{L}_{L1}^{hole} are L1 losses computed over unmasked and masked regions respectively, and $\mathcal{L}_{perceptual}$ is a VGG16 feature-space loss (Johnson et al., 2016). Pix2Pix additionally includes an LSGAN adversarial loss (weight 0.1) after epoch 5. The diffusion model is trained to directly predict the clean image x_0 from noisy inputs using an MSE reconstruction loss, rather than predicting the noise term.

Mixed-precision training (AMP) with gradient clipping (max norm 1.0) is applied throughout. Batches yielding NaN loss are skipped; early stopping with patience 30 (evaluated every 5 epochs) terminates training if validation PSNR does not improve.

4. Results

4.1. Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative evaluation of our models across both grayscale and colored datasets reveals significant performance variations, as detailed in Table 1.

During evaluation, known (unmasked) regions are directly preserved from the ground truth image, and reconstruction quality is assessed on the composite output. As a result, reported metrics primarily reflect reconstruction performance in masked regions, as unmasked pixels are directly preserved from ground truth. Key findings from the quantitative analysis: RFA-Net achieves the best overall performance: highest PSNR on colored data (26.53 dB), best SSIM in both modes (0.8760 B&W, 0.8877 colored), and best LPIPS in both modes (0.0993 B&W, 0.0979 colored), with a moderate 25.29M parameters and fast inference at 0.002-0.003s per image.

Figure 3 – Grayscale reconstruction comparisons across all seven models. **Green boxes** highlight RFA-Net (best structural continuity); **red boxes** highlight Guided DDPM (weakest reconstruction).

DeepRes U-Net is competitive (23.51 dB B&W, 26.34 dB colored) but at 65.98M parameters and the slowest non-diffusion inference (0.046s). PConv U-Net, with only 4.05M parameters, is the most efficient model and remains viable for resource-constrained settings. Guided DDPM underperforms convolutional models on grayscale (PSNR 21.84 dB) but recovers in colored mode (24.77 dB), suggesting sensitivity to channel information. RGB training consistently outperforms grayscale by 2.7-2.9 dB PSNR across all models, attributable to additional texture priors from the colorization pipeline. LPIPS is computed over the full reconstructed image, which may favor perceptually plausible outputs even when structural accuracy is slightly reduced.

4.2. Qualitative Evaluation

Figures 3 and 4 present comparative reconstructions across all seven models, showing held-out intact seals with programmatically generated damage masks and the corresponding model predictions.

Qualitative observations reveal several key patterns:

- **Script Reconstruction:** RFA-Net best maintained Indus script stroke continuity (Figure 3), owing to its multi-scale dilated convolutions capturing fine engraved detail.

Figure 4 – Colored reconstruction comparisons across all seven models. **Green box**: RFA-Net (highest PSNR 26.53 dB, best SSIM). **Red box**: Guided DDPM (lowest PSNR and SSIM in colored mode).

- **Texture Preservation**: RFA-Net and DeepRes U-Net most accurately reproduced steatite surface textures, as visible in the difference maps of Figure 5.
- **Color Handling**: In colored reconstructions (Figures 4 and 6), RFA-Net produced the most plausible color distributions with minimal difference-map error in intact script regions, while Guided DDPM produced blurry, low-fidelity outputs.
- **Iconographic Elements**: All models struggled with complex animal motifs (e.g., unicorn figures), with reconstruction quality notably lower than for script elements.
- **Efficiency vs. Quality**: PConv U-Net, with only 4.05M parameters, produced visually acceptable results for small damage regions, representing a strong lightweight baseline.

4.3. Computational Efficiency

Inference speed varied significantly across architectures, as reported in Table 1. Context Encoder and Pix2Pix are the fastest non-diffusion models (< 0.001s per image), while DeepRes U-Net is the slowest among convolutional models (0.046s) due to its 65.98M parameters and SE blocks. RFA-Net offers the best trade-off, achieving top perceptual metrics at 0.002-0.003s

Figure 5 – Detailed per-sample restoration pipeline for the best-performing model (DeepRes U-Net, grayscale): ground truth, damage mask, damaged input, restored output, and pixel-difference map.

per image. Guided DDPM is an order of magnitude slower ($\approx 0.265s$) due to its 50-step iterative reverse diffusion sampling, making it impractical for large-scale seal analysis without further optimization.

5. Discussion

The qualitative and quantitative results reveal clear distinctions across the seven evaluated architectures. RFA-Net consistently achieves the strongest results, producing sharp reconstructions with high continuity between masked and unmasked regions. Its multi-scale dilated convolutions and SE attention blocks effectively capture both coarse structure and fine engraved detail inherent to Harappan seals. DeepRes U-Net achieves comparable PSNR on grayscale data but at nearly three times the parameter count, offering diminishing returns relative to its computational cost.

Pix2Pix reconstructs primary structure reasonably well but introduces blurred or oversimplified textures, particularly under large missing regions. Context Encoder, despite its simpler encoder-decoder design with no skip connections, performs competitively given its 13.90M parameters, suggesting that global context modeling contributes meaningfully to seal restoration. PConv U-Net, the most parameter-efficient model at 4.05M, produces acceptable results for localized damage but degrades on larger masked regions where its limited capacity becomes a bottleneck.

Figure 6 – Detailed restoration pipeline for RFA-Net (colored mode): ground truth, damage mask, damaged input, restored output, and pixel-difference map. Bright regions in the difference map indicate areas of higher reconstruction uncertainty.

Guided DDPM underperforms convolutional models on grayscale (PSNR 21.84 dB, LPIPS 0.1146) but recovers partially in colored mode (PSNR 24.77 dB), suggesting sensitivity to channel information. With fewer than 800 training images, the model cannot fully stabilize the reverse diffusion process, confirming that diffusion architectures require substantially more data than is currently available for this domain. Consequently, RFA-Net emerged as the most robust and practical framework for this specific restoration challenge, balancing accuracy, perceptual quality, parameter efficiency, and inference speed. The relatively limited dataset size and reduced diffusion steps used in this study may constrain the performance of diffusion-based models compared to convolutional architectures.

The use of generative models on undeciphered script requires caution: models may hallucinate non-existent symbols or iconographic elements, and outputs could be mistaken for authentic evidence. We recommend three safeguards: (1) *provenance marking*, AI outputs must be watermarked and stored separately from original scan data; (2) *expert validation*, script regions should be reviewed by archaeologists before any scholarly use; and (3) *uncertainty visualization*, the pixel-difference maps in Figure 5 flag speculative regions, and future work should expose per-pixel confidence estimates directly in model outputs.

6. Conclusion

This study investigates deep learning approaches for reconstructing damaged Harappan seals through extensive comparative experiments. Our empirical results show that generative models can successfully restore missing regions while preserving both structural integrity and fine surface details essential for archaeological study. The evaluation across multiple metrics confirms that these techniques achieve strong performance in reconstructing script elements and iconographic features, with particular effectiveness in handling different types of seal degradation. The newly created dataset of annotated seal images and the proposed evaluation protocol address a critical gap in digital heritage research.

For future work, four key directions emerge from our experimental findings: (1) enhancing the training data with more varied examples of rare seal types and complex damage patterns, (2) developing specialized techniques to better handle the unique characteristics of undeciphered scripts, (3) incorporating archaeological domain knowledge directly into the reconstruction process, and (4) extending the framework to leverage 3D seal representations where available. These improvements would further bridge the gap between computational methods and archaeological conservation needs while maintaining the rigorous experimental approach demonstrated in this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the American University of Sharjah for computational resources.

References

- Baglioni, M., Poggi, G., Chelazzi, D., and Baglioni, P. (2021). Advanced materials in cultural heritage conservation. *Molecules*, 26(13):3967.
- Cao, F., Gousseau, Y., Masnou, S., and Pérez, P. (2011). Geometrically guided exemplar-based inpainting. *SIAM J. Img. Sci.*, 4(4):1143–1179.
- Deng, X. and Yu, Y. (2023). Ancient mural inpainting via structure information guided two-branch model. *Heritage Science*, 11(1):131.
- Farajzadeh, N. and Hashemzadeh, M. (2021). A deep neural network based framework for restoring the damaged persian pottery via digital inpainting. *Journal of Computational Science*, 56:101486.
- He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., and Sun, J. (2016). Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 770–778.
- Ho, J., Jain, A., and Abbeel, P. (2020). Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 33:6840–6851.
- Hu, J., Shen, L., and Sun, G. (2018). Squeeze-and-excitation networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 7132–7141.
- Huang, S. and Hong, L. (2023). Diffusion model for mural image inpainting. In *2023 IEEE 7th Information Technology and Mechatronics Engineering Conference (ITOEC)*, volume 7, pages 886–890. IEEE.
- Idris, M. Z., Mustafa, N. B., and Yusoff, S. O. S. (2016). Preservation of intangible cultural heritage using advance digital technology: Issues and challenges. *Harmonia: Journal of Arts Research and Education*, 16(1):1–13.
- Internet Archive (2024). Internet archive. Accessed: 2025-05-04.
- Isola, P., Zhu, J.-Y., Zhou, T., and Efros, A. A. (2017). Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 1125–1134.

- Jboor, N. H., Belhi, A., Al-Ali, A. K., Bouras, A., and Jaoua, A. (2019). Towards an inpainting framework for visual cultural heritage. In *2019 IEEE Jordan International Joint Conference on Electrical Engineering and Information Technology (JEEIT)*, pages 602–607. IEEE.
- Johnson, J., Alahi, A., and Fei-Fei, L. (2016). Perceptual losses for real-time style transfer and super-resolution. In *European conference on computer vision*, pages 694–711. Springer.
- Kaur, A., Raj, A., Jayanthi, N., and Indu, S. (2020). Inpainting of irregular holes in a manuscript using unet and partial convolution. In *2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA)*, pages 778–784. IEEE.
- Kumar, P. and Gupta, V. (2023). Unpaired image-to-image translation based artwork restoration using generative adversarial networks. In *International Conference on Intelligent Manufacturing and Energy Sustainability*, pages 581–591. Springer.
- Kumar, P., Gupta, V., and Grover, M. (2024). Dual attention and channel transformer based generative adversarial network for restoration of the damaged artwork. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 128:107457.
- Liu, G., Reda, F. A., Shih, K. J., Wang, T.-C., Tao, A., and Catanzaro, B. (2018). Image inpainting for irregular holes using partial convolutions. In *Proceedings of the European conference on computer vision (ECCV)*, pages 85–100.
- Liu, J., Zhang, W., Tang, Y., Tang, J., and Wu, G. (2020). Residual feature aggregation network for image super-resolution. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 2359–2368.
- Lugmayr, A., Danelljan, M., Romero, A., Yu, F., Timofte, R., and Van Gool, L. (2022). Repaint: Inpainting using denoising diffusion probabilistic models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 11461–11471.
- Lv, C., Li, Z., Shen, Y., Li, J., and Zheng, J. (2022). Separafill: Two generators connected mural image restoration based on generative adversarial network with skip connect. *Heritage Science*, 10(1):135.
- Mahadevan, I. (1991). *Corpus of Indus Seals and Inscriptions: Collections in Pakistan*, volume 86 of *Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India*. Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi.
- Mahadevan, I. (1998). *Corpus of Indus Seals and Inscriptions: Collections in India*. Indian Council of Historical Research and the American Institute of Indian Studies, New Delhi.
- Mukhopadhyay, B. A. (2023). Semantic scope of indus inscriptions comprising taxation, trade and craft licensing, commodity control and access control: archaeological and script-internal evidence. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1):972.
- Nanetti, A. (2021). Defining heritage science: A consilience pathway to treasuring the complexity of inheritable human experiences through historical method, ai, and ml. *Complexity*, 2021(1):4703820.
- Palaniappan, S. and Adhikari, R. (2017). Deep learning the indus script. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.00523*.
- Pathak, D., Krahenbuhl, P., Donahue, J., Darrell, T., and Efros, A. A. (2016). Context encoders: Feature learning by inpainting. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 2536–2544.
- Perrin, S., Cudilla, L., Xie, Y., Mouchère, H., and Marthot-Santaniello, I. (2023). Homer restored: Virtual reconstruction of papyrus bodmer 1. HIP '23, pages 37–42, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P., and Brox, T. (2015). U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In *International Conference on Medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention*, pages 234–241. Springer.
- Sumathi, G. and Uma Devi, M. (2024a). Inpainting of damaged temple murals using edge- and line-guided diffusion patch gan. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, Volume 7 - 2024.
- Sumathi, G. and Uma Devi, M. (2024b). Inpainting of damaged temple murals using edge-and line-guided diffusion patch gan. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 7:1453847.
- Sun, Z., Lei, Y., and Wu, X. (2024). Ancient paintings inpainting based on dual encoders and contextual information. *Heritage Science*, 12(1):266.

- Wang, Y., Xiao, M., Hu, Y., Yan, J., and Zhu, Z. (2024). Research on restoration of murals based on diffusion model and transformer. *Computers, Materials & Continua*, 80(3):4433–4449.
- Witzel, M. (2019). Early 'aryans' and their neighbors outside and inside india. *Journal of biosciences*, 44:1–10.
- Xu, T., Huang, T.-Z., Deng, L.-J., Zhao, X.-L., and Hu, J.-F. (2022). Exemplar-based image inpainting using adaptive two-stage structure-tensor based priority function and nonlocal filtering. *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, 83:103430.
- Xu, Z., Zhang, C., and Wu, Y. (2023). Digital inpainting of mural images based on dc-cyclegan. *Heritage Science*, 11(1):169.
- Xu, Z., Zhang, X., Chen, W., Liu, J., Xu, T., and Wang, Z. (2024). Muraldiff: Diffusion for ancient murals restoration on large-scale pre-training. *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*.
- Yadav, A. K., Sharma, S., Kumar, R., and Dhiraj (2024). Revitalizing ancient murals in the shekhawati region through image inpainting techniques. In *2024 11th International Conference on Signal Processing and Integrated Networks (SPIN)*, pages 361–366.
- Yu, W., Hu, Z., Cao, L., and Li, Z. (2022). Mural inpainting method based on deep convolutional generative adversarial networks. In *Interdisciplinary Research for Printing and Packaging*, pages 71–77. Springer.
- Zhao, J., Tan, J., Huang, Y., and Lu, C. (2022). Improved image inpainting exemplar-based algorithms by boundary priori-knowledge. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 355:03004.
- Zhong, X., Chen, W., Guo, Z., Zhang, J., and Luo, H. (2025). Image inpainting using diffusion models to restore eaves tile patterns in chinese heritage buildings. *Automation in Construction*, 171:105997.
- Zhu, S., Xue, H., Nie, N., Zhu, C., Liu, H., and Fang, P. (2024). Reproducing the past: A dataset for benchmarking inscription restoration. In *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, pages 7714–7723.